

Study of cohesion and allied properties of ammonium halide crystals

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Abstract : A study of cohesion and allied properties of ammonium halides has been carried out using an interionic potential which consists of long range coulomb interaction, van der Waals interaction (vdWI), due to dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole interactions, three-body interaction (TBI) and a short range overlap repulsive interaction proposed by Ali *et al.* [*Physica (B)*, 1991, 168, 121] operative up to second nearest neighbour. The values of cohesive energy, isothermal bulk-modulus, Debye temperature, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter and Grüneisen parameters (using Slater, Dugdale and McDonald and Free-Volume theories) have been calculated. The results obtained agree well with the available experimental data.

Keywords : Interionic potential, ammonium halide crystals, cohesive energy, bulk modulus, Debye temperature, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter, Grüneisen parameters.

Introduction

In order to have better understanding of the interionic forces that bind the atoms of the crystals together, the study of cohesion and associated properties of the crystals is of fundamental importance. The major part of this cohesion is contributed by the long-range (LR) coulomb interaction which is counter balanced by the short-range (SR) overlap repulsive interaction, which has its origin from Pauli's principle.

In recent years a number of interaction potentials¹⁻⁹ have been developed and employed for the prediction of various properties of ionic crystals. A detailed survey of the literature reveals that most of these potentials mentioned above have been used for thorough and extensive study of the cohesive and allied properties of alkali halides. However such detailed studies have not been made for ammonium halides, which are basically ionic in nature. The ammonium halides thus present an interesting system for the study, in view of their polymorphism and possible internal rotation of ammonium ions¹⁰. NH₄Cl and NH₄Br along with their deuterated counterparts have CsCl structure. Another important feature of ammonium halides is that they are basically ionic in nature and violate Cauchy's relation ($C_{11}=C_{44}$) similar to the alkali halides.

The first successful attempt to predict the cohesive energy of NH₄Cl and NH₄Br crystals was made by Bleick¹¹

who used Born-Mayer (BM) potential for SR repulsive interaction effective up to next nearest neighbour and incorporated the effect of vdWI using d-d and d-q interaction coefficients estimated by Mayer² from perturbation theory^{13,14}. Recently Murty and Murti¹⁵ have calculated the cohesive energy of ammonium halides using Fumi-Tosi potential and vdWI coefficients estimated by Mayer². These studies show a considerable disagreement between the theoretical and experimental values of cohesive energy. Several authors^{15,16} have emphasized that the expression of vdWI coefficients derived from perturbation theory contain excitation energy parameters which are subjected to considerable uncertainties. It is also known that in addition to the LR coulomb and SR repulsive interactions, the van der Waal interactions also play an important role in describing the cohesive energy and allied properties of ionic solids^{8,9}. So any shortcoming in the evaluation of vdWI coefficients might lead to significant errors.

Keeping in view all the facts mentioned above, we have formulated an interionic potential which consists of LR coulomb interaction, vdW dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole interactions using the Slater-Kirkwood variation (SKV) method¹⁷ for evaluation the vdWI coefficients due to d-d and d-q interactions and three-body interaction (TBI), which has been found to play an important role in describing various static and dynamic properties of ionic solids¹⁸⁻²¹ and a complex form of SR repulsive interac-

tion potential proposed by Ali *et al.*²² and effective up to the second nearest neighbouring ions. The potential proposed here has been used to calculate the cohesive energy, isothermal bulk modulus, Debye temperature, Moelwyn-Hughes parameter and Grüneisen parameters.

Theoretical approach :

The crystal energy of an ionic solid due to interaction between ions can be expressed as

$$W = W_c + W_v + W_{TB} + W_{SR} \quad (1)$$

The first term represents the Coulomb energy

$$W_c = - \frac{Az_1z_2e^2}{r} \quad (2)$$

with A as the Madelung constant and r is the separation between ammonium and halide ions.

The second term is vdWI energy

$$W_v = - \frac{C}{r^6} - \frac{D}{r^8} \quad (3)$$

due to d-d and d-q interactions. C and D represents vdWI coefficients due to these interactions.

The third term in eq. (1) is the three-body interaction (TBI) energy

$$W_{TB} = - \frac{nz_1z_2e^2}{r} f(r) \quad (4)$$

where n is a constant dependent on the crystal structure. TBI arises from the charge transfer effect¹⁸ between the adjacent ions and $f(r)$ is TBI parameter dependent on overlap integral^{19,20}. This function is the measure of inter-ionic size difference and its existence in ionic crystals is well established from Quantum Mechanical theories²¹.

The last term is the short-range overlap repulsive energy which on considering the next nearest neighbouring (NNN) interactions is expressed as

$$W_{SR} = MP \beta_{ij} r_{ij}^{-2} \exp(-b_{ij} r_{ij}^N) + M'P [\beta_{ii} r_{ii}^{-2} \exp(-b_{ii} r_{ii}^N) + \beta_{jj} r_{jj}^{-2} \exp(-b_{jj} r_{jj}^N)] \quad (5)$$

where M and M' are the number of NN and NNN for the given structure, $r_{ii} = r_{jj} = 1.1547r$ for CsCl and P is the repulsive strength parameter and b_{ij} , b_{ii} and b_{jj} are the repulsive hardness parameters to represent the cation-anion, cation-cation and anion-anion pair interactions.

β_{ij} are the Puling coefficients expressed as,

$$\beta_{ij} = 1 + \frac{Z_i}{n_i} + \frac{Z_j}{n_j} \quad (6)$$

where Z_i and Z_j are the valencies of i and j ions and n_i and n_j are the number of outer most electrons in cations and anions respectively.

Method of evaluation of potential parameters :

The repulsive strength parameter P is evaluated by applying crystal stability condition

$$(dW/dr)_{r=r_0} = 0 \quad (7)$$

we get,

$$\frac{P}{r_0^2} = \frac{R}{S} \quad (8)$$

where

$$R = 2\{Ae^2r_0^{-1} + 6Cr_0^{-6} + 8Dr_0^{-8}\} + nAe^2r_0^{-1} \{f(r_0) - r_0f'(r_0)\} \quad (9)$$

and

$$S = M\beta_{+-} \exp(-b_{+-} r_0^N) (3b_{+-} r_0^N + 4) + \frac{M'}{2k_1^2} + \{\beta_{++} \exp(-b_{++}k_1^N r_0^N) (3b_{++}k_1^N r_0^N + 4) + \beta_{--} \exp(-b_{--}k_1^N r_0^N) (3b_{--}k_1^N r_0^N + 4)\} \quad (10)$$

with $k_1 = 1.1547$.

The values of r_0 used in the above calculation have been taken from Bleick¹² and Mayer², while those of C and D from Vachaspati *et al.*²⁴.

The repulsive hardness parameters (b_{+-} , b_{++} and b_{--}) are evaluated using the relations suggested by Ali *et al.*²².

$$b_{+-} = (z_1z_2)^p (\rho_{+-}^{-N}) / (k + 3.8) \quad (11)$$

$$b_{++} = (b_{+-})/k \quad (12)$$

and

$$b_{--} = (3b_{+-})/(k+m) \quad (13)$$

where $p = 0.12$, $m = 2$, $N = 1.5$ and $k = 1.54$ for CsCl structure. The values of ρ_{+-} have been taken from Rana *et al.*²⁵.

The TBI parameter $f(r)$ and its derivatives have been evaluated using Cauchy relation²⁶ and Cochran relation²⁷. For CsCl structure

$$C_{12}-C_{44} = 12.213 e^2 r_0^{-4} [r_0f'(r_0)] \quad (14)$$

and

$$f(r) = f_0(r) \exp(-r/\rho_{+-}) \quad (15)$$

where $f_0(r)$ is a constant.

The values of second order elastic constants (SOEC) used in the calculations are taken from Mayer² and Ladd *et al.*²³. The computed value of P , (b_{+-} , b_{++} and b_{--}) and $f(r)$ are listed in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Calculation of thermodynamic properties :

The crystal energy W , is calculated from eq. (1). The results are compared with experimental data²¹. In order to show the relative importance of the role played by various interactions we have computed their contributions separately which are listed in Table 3.

For evaluating isothermal bulk modulus (B_T), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1) and Debye temperature, we make

use of the following expressions

$$B_T = \frac{r_0^2 w''(r_0)}{9V} \quad (16)$$

$$C_1 = \left(\frac{dB_T}{dP} \right) = 1 - \frac{r_0 w'''(r_0)}{3w''(r_0)} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\theta_D = \frac{\hbar}{k_B} \left(\frac{5r_0 B_T}{\mu} \right)^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

All the calculated values are listed in Table 4 along with available literature data^{24,26,28}.

Anharmonic properties :

Grüneisen parameter (γ) gives a measure of the

Table 1. Values of input data for ammonium halide crystals; equilibrium interionic separation (r_0 ; Å), repulsive hardness parameter (ρ_{+-} ; Å), vdW constants (C ; 10^{-60} erg cm⁶ and D ; 10^{-76} erg cm⁸), potential parameters (P ; 10^{-26} erg cm²) and (b_{+-} , b_{++} and b_{--} all in 10^{12} cm^{-N})

Crystal	r_0	ρ_{+-} Ref. 25	C Ref. 24	D Ref. 24	P	b_{+-}	b_{++}	b_{--}
NH ₄ Cl	3.3480 ^a	0.307	2228.050	1055.796	8.63103	1.10093	0.71489	0.93299
NH ₄ Br	3.5100 ^a	0.385	4178.563	2213.666	3.35445	0.78393	0.50905	0.66435
ND ₄ Cl	3.3070 ^b	0.304	2008.560	980.177	8.05578	1.11727	0.72550	0.94684
ND ₄ Br	3.5100 ^a	0.395	4174.673	2210.850	2.88517	0.75435	0.48984	0.63928

^aRef. 12, ^bRef. 2.

Table 2. Values of SOEC data ($C_{\alpha\beta}$, 10^{11} dynes cm⁻²) as in put data and TBI parameter and its derivative (dimensionless)

Crystal	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	$f(r)$	$rf'(r_0)$
NH ₄ Cl	4.740 ^a	1.640 ^a	1.436 ^a	-0.01788	0.00937
NH ₄ Br	3.429 ^b	0.772 ^b	0.761 ^b	-0.01630	0.00059
ND ₄ Cl	4.790 ^a	1.640 ^a	1.430 ^a	-0.01934	0.00892
ND ₄ Br	3.429 ^b	0.772 ^b	0.761 ^b	-0.01630	0.00059

^aRef. 2, ^bRef. 23.

anharmonicity of atomic vibration in crystals. The thermodynamic definition of this parameter is

$$\gamma = -d(\ln v_i)/d(\ln V) \quad (19)$$

where v_i is the frequency of oscillation of the crystal and V is its volume.

The basic theory of γ was proposed by Slater²⁹ on the basis of theory of elasticity. His expression for vibration

Table 3. Calculated values of coulomb energy (W_c), vdW energy (W_V), TBI energy (W_{TB}), short-range repulsive energy (W_{SR}) and cohesive energy (W) (all in kcal mol⁻¹)

Crystal	W_c	W_V	W_{TB}	W_{SR}	Present	W (or W_{Total})		
						others		Expt.
						Ref. 24	Ref. 25	Ref. 21
NH ₄ Cl	-174.775	-23.764	25.000	25.084	-148.455	-143.898	-148.398	-150.2
NH ₄ Br	-166.709	-33.550	21.739	28.333	-140.187	-136.237	-130.477	-143.0
ND ₄ Cl	-176.942	-23.092	27.377	25.057	-147.600	-143.873	-147.770	-150.0
ND ₄ Br	-166.709	-33.518	21.739	39.409	-139.079	-136.237	-130.477	-143.0
Av. % dev.					1.87	4.44	5.06	

Table 4. Calculated values of isothermal bulk modulus (B_T ; 10^{12} dynes cm^{-1}), Moelwyn-Hughes parameter (C_1 ; dimensionless) and Debye temperature (θ_D , K)

Crystal	B_T			C_1		θ_D	
	Present	Others		Present	Others	Present	Others
		Ref. 12	Ref. 26				
NH ₄ Cl	0.2582	0.1792	0.2674	5.2732	5.2726	355.1107	351.8187
NH ₄ Br	0.1658	0.1553	0.1961	4.2822	4.2818	262.7203	261.4578
ND ₄ Cl	0.2690	0.2381	0.2449	5.3170	5.3179	337.8051	338.7744
ND ₄ Br	0.1658	0.1553	0.1961	4.7063	4.7058	242.4459	241.786

velocities are valid only if the solid is under zero external pressure. Dugdala and McDonald³⁰ derived a general expression for γ by considering the effect of pressure. But these two theories did not consider the variation of Poisson's ratio with volume³¹. Vaschenko and Zubarov³² developed a formulation of γ using free-volume theory. Recently Migault and Romain³² proposed a unification of these theories considering the variation of Poisson's ratio with volume and deduced a general expression for γ .

$$\gamma = -\frac{4-3S}{6} - \frac{V}{2} \frac{d^2(PV^S)/dV^2}{d(PV^S)/dV} \quad (20)$$

where P is the pressure at volume V and absolute temperature T , S is a parameter whose values is zero for all solids in Slater theory, 2/3 in DM theory and 4/3 in free-volume (FV) theory.

The simplified form of the above eq. gives a direct relationship between γ and $\left(\frac{dB_T}{dP}\right)$ as

$$\gamma_S = -\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dB_T}{dP}\right) \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_{DM} = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dB_T}{dP}\right) \quad (22)$$

and

$$\gamma_{FV} = -\frac{5}{6} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dB_T}{dP}\right) \quad (23)$$

The value of γ_S , γ_{DM} and γ_{FV} using the above relations are listed in Table 5 along with available literature data³⁴.

Results and discussion

It is seen from Table 3, that our calculated values of

Table 5. Calculated values of γ_S , γ_{DM} and γ_{FV} (all dimensionless)

Crystal	Grüneisen parameters			Expt. Ref. 34
	γ_S	γ_{DM}	γ_{FV}	
NH ₄ Cl	2.4699	2.1366	1.8032	2.004
NH ₄ Br	1.9744	1.6411	1.3077	2.013
ND ₄ Cl	2.4918	2.1585	1.8251	2.349
ND ₄ Br	2.1865	1.8532	1.5198	2.013

cohesive energy are closer to the experimental values²¹ compared to those reported by Vachaspati *et al.*²⁴ and Rana *et al.*²⁵. The reason for the improved agreement seems to be the use of properly estimated values of vdW coefficients and inclusion of three-body interaction effects in the crystal energy which are quite dominant in ammonium halide crystals (as indicated in Table 3) and their effects must be incorporated for a realistic representation of the interionic forces in these crystals. It is also seen from the table that our calculated values of B_T agree well with the values reported by Lundqvist²⁶. Further the computed values of C_1 and θ_D are in excellent agreement with the literature data reported by Vachaspati *et al.*²⁴ and Karlson²⁸ respectively.

The computed values of γ_S , γ_{DM} and γ_{FV} are reported in Table 5 and compared with the available literature data³⁴. It is seen that the values of γ_S closely resemble the experimental values compared to those of γ_{DM} and γ_{FV} .

Finally we may conclude that the interionic potential model used in the present study has explained reasonably well the cohesive energy and other thermodynamic and elastic properties of NH₄Cl and NH₄Br along with their deuterated counterparts. However the discrepancy still existing between our theoretical results and experimental data may be due to exclusion of anharmonic effects and order-disorder phenomena in these crystals.

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